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MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF TEEMING OF STEELMAKING LADLES

Rishikesh Mishra¹, Dipak Mazumdar²

Department of Materials Science and Engineering

Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, INDIA

(1. Graduate Student; 2. Professor)

Corresponding author's email: mrishi@iitk.ac.in

Abstract: In order to develop better mathematical understanding of drainage dynamics during emptying of steelmaking reactors, numerical modeling has been carried out. As a typical example, transport funnels formed during draining of water models of ladle and similar geometries was investigated. Towards this, a RANS based, 3D, transient approach embodying realizable $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence and multiphase VOF formulations was developed. ANSYS Fluent™ was used to carry out the simulations. Computed results together with scaled model experiments indicated that predictions of fundamental flow dynamics were physically realistic and in line with scientific evidence. However, on a quantitative scale, apparently systematic deviation from the physical model results was noted. Potential reasons are discussed in the presentation and in such context, the role of prior stirring, natural convection (non-isothermal modeling) and tracking of the unsteady period of funnel development are highlighted.

Keywords: Slag entrainment, multiphase modeling, vortex formation, ladle metallurgy

1. Introduction

The formation of slag transport funnels during ladle drainage is a major deterrent to process efficiency. The outflow volume develops a core extending from slag-metal interface to the outlet, appearing as shown in Fig. 1. The transported slag is dispersed into refined steel in the subsequent tundish, damaging product composition and cleanliness. Consequently, ladle drainage is halted with a minimum residual steel, at the appearance of slag transport. Understanding and modeling it becomes important in terms of process design, as sophisticated monitoring of bath dynamics becomes difficult and expensive, with limited precision because of high operating temperatures and visual opacity of steel-slag system.

In research through physical modeling, water and mercury are well-accepted as steel equivalents for cold model experiments^[1-5] to understand the effect of process design parameters. Numerical modeling^[6-8] takes a root cause analysis approach, starting with and building upon the fundamental mathematics behind flow physics. Advances in computational efficiency have made numerical simulation an increasingly viable alternative to physical modeling exercises, partly due to difficulty of modeling and handling physical experiments, combined with the ability to explicitly model and investigate the minutiae of flow physics in

simulations. However, numerical modeling exercises have often limited themselves to single or two fluid (steel-air) systems, whereas three dimensional, transient systems with three or more phases (steel-slag-air) are known to differ significantly its simpler counterparts^[1].

Figure 1 A developed transport funnel (Water and mustard oil)

2. Investigation

In order to study the evolution of slag transport funnels a transient three dimensional turbulent multiphase model was developed based on Volume of Fluid (VOF) approach to capture phase interaction. Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations are solved for mixture velocity. Realizable $k-\varepsilon$ model^[9,10] for turbulent viscosity

was adopted to calculate effective viscosity in the system under turbulent bath dynamics.

The numerical model's accuracy was evaluated using a cylindrical water bath, with mustard oil and petroleum ether used to simulate two varieties of overlying liquid. Table 1 summarizes physical properties of simulated fluid phases.

Table 1 Physical properties of multiphase fluid systems

Fluid	Density (kg/m^3)	Viscosity ($mPa.s$)	Surface (air) (N/m)	Tension (water) (N/m)
Water	998	1.003	0.072	-
Petroleum Ether	640	0.38	0.044	0.016
Mustard Oil	919	70	0.051	0.035
Air	1.225	0.018	-	0.072

The system was stagnated and bottom drained through a centrally located nozzle of variable size. Numerically obtained values for critical bath height, H_{cr} of these stagnant baths were found to predict experimental values reasonably well, with less than 10% error compared to physically observed funnels. Parametric analysis on the model's results indicated outlet size and upper phase density to be dominant factors, along with initial state of motion in the bath, while the initial height of liquid (initial size of bath) was found to be largely inconsequential.

Strong influence of pre-existing tangential velocity field was evident in simulations where prior to drainage, a steady state rotation of 180° per second (30 RPM) was induced at the wall of the cylindrical bath. Compared to drainage of an identical multiphase system from stagnant state, funnel development was expediated on account of vortex effect, resulting in a 30% increase in H_{cr} .

After validating the model's accuracy experimentally, it was then used to predict flow dynamics in a scaled down water model of 140t eccentrically drained ladle. In the physical setup, the ladle was filled with water to the height of 600 mm (equal to the ladle diameter), topped with a 20 mm layer of petroleum ether and agitated to a steady state of circulation by bottom injection of air. This was followed by a standby time of 15 minutes to allow decay of residual velocity^[11] before draining the bath eccentrically from nozzle located at $D/4$, expecting a well stagnated bath. The corresponding

simulation was run from a stagnant state of bath at height 320 mm ($\sim 0.5D$), based on the observed independence of H_{cr} from initial bath height during investigations with the cylindrical bath.

3. Discussion

The numerical system was found to grossly under-predict the critical bath height at which entrainment starts (0.1D), expecting its occurrence significantly later than physical observation (0.19D).

Table 1 shows the predicted values of normalized critical bath height H_{cr}/D , under similar relative outlet diameter, d/D , for the two physical systems. Compared to the cylindrical bath, simulation of ladle drainage predicts a much lower value of H_{cr} , one that might be attributed to the role played by nozzle eccentricity^[5,14]. Contrary to this, the corresponding physical observations in the two baths are much closer in value.

Table 2 Comparison of critical height across geometries

Vessel	d/D	H_{cr}/D , actual	H_{cr}/D , predicted
Cylindrical bath	0.06	0.17	0.17
Model ladle	0.04	0.19	0.10

In terms of process design, stirring of ladle using gas injection appears to be the primary differentiating factor between the two physical systems discussed, in addition to the location of drainage nozzle. Such systemic differences encourage a discussion on the elements of mathematical modeling, their apparent implications on accuracy of modeling time-evolving transport funnels, particularly in the context of slag entrainment particularly but also steel melting and refinement dynamics in general.

3.1 Elements of mathematical modeling

It is notable that standby times prior to drainage are comparable for both systems, and therefore, so is the expected degree of stagnation. However, looking at the role of tangential velocity field and the low likelihood of violation of nozzle eccentricity effect, the role of residual velocity appears more probable behind the observed inconsistency in bath heights, *ie* the physical ladle may not have achieved true stagnation as in case of the cylindrical bath.

Based on observations, the modeling of initial velocity field appears to be one such important

element. In steelmaking ladles, these velocity residuals may typically be generated from end-stage Argon bubbling prior to drainage. As the gas injection rate and angle are controlled parameters, tailoring the gas-liquid dynamic towards end of refining can be a possible method to tailor the subsequent flow during drainage.

For modeling industrial non-isothermal steel-slag systems, temperature dynamics of the bath play a significant role in influencing flow behavior. Temperature gradients and consequent density changes lead to buoyant natural convection, sinking colder metal along the ladle wall, while the hotter core rises and spreads out. These vertical eddies have been found to accelerate drain sink formation.^[6]

Identifying and modeling elements of the flow provide a way to understand the influence of various sources of momentum and analyze the evolution in their presence.

3.2 Analytical understanding of flow evolution

Teeming of ladle and associated flow phenomena are primarily driven by body forces, *ie* gravity and inertial interaction. The development of gravity driven vortices, such as slag transport funnels, can be segmented into stages:

- i. The appearance of dimple at the fluid interface close to the axis of drainage, indicating a visible onset of downward pull on the upper phase.
- ii. Downward extension of the dimple towards the nozzle, as the pull by the outflow gets stronger.
- iii. Formation of a fully developed funnel core extending from interface to outflow orifice. The flux of steel in outflow decreases sharply, replaced instead by the entrained slag.

Tracking the unsteady, developing stage of the evolving funnel brought to notice an important flow phenomenon. In the developing stage of funnel in physical drainage, the formation of surface dimple is followed by a sustained period where particulate quanta of slag (petroleum ether) are seen to break away from the bulk and down the funnel's core. This droplet transport continues for a significant period of time (approximately 12 s) before a fully formed funnel develops. Fig. 2 shows an instance of this period of particulate entrainment. No such correspondence was seen in earlier experiments in the cylindrical bath.

Figure 2 Unsteady entrainment of particulates

It is notable that while the numerical model does not capture critical bath height with accuracy, and is without a possibly critical presence of residual velocity fields, it nevertheless shows evidence of particulate entrainment. Tracking the volume fraction contours of model slag gives an understanding of the movement of fluid interfaces. In the moments preceding funnel formation, as bath height drops to approach H_{cr} , discrete quanta of slag are recorded traveling down the outflow stream, as seen in Fig. 3.

Figure 3 Unsteady period of entrainment as seen in the numerical model

A fully developed gravity driven vortex is characterized dominantly by these body forces. However, the simplistic model of evolution in the form of a continuum of slag moving downward, as

discussed earlier, might not be an apt representation to capture particulate entrainment of slag. While the primary forces driving the flow do not change, the unsteady period might see a more pronounced effect of interfacial shear and adhesion-cohesion dynamic of the multi-fluid system. If so, a fluid with high viscosity would not be expected to undergo particulate shearing by local relative motions.

Such subtleties in bath dynamics stress upon the importance of designing a numerical model with ability to capture flow intricacies, an exercise in translating real world physics into a mathematical order.

3.3 Suitability of modeling approach

While alternative formulations have been explored^[7], multiphase VOF models, being suitable for immiscible fluid continua, are the method of choice for bulk steel-slag interactions, such as in the current investigation. It might appear that in the context of droplet entrainment during funnel development, a Large Eddy Simulation (LES) based approach (instead of RANS based) can be better suited to capture interface perturbations and fluctuations over small length scales. However, two arguments discourage this choice: LES is associated with high computational expense compared to RANS based approach; and as seen in Fig. 3, the currently applied model should not be dismissed as incapable of capturing these slag droplets, but rather explored for improvement in flow capturing precision.

The sharpness of interfaces captured via VOF tracking directly depends on the grid refinement, although it comes with the drawback of computational intensity. A computationally optimized treatment can be explored utilizing dynamic local refinement of the spatial domain, with detailed meshing around the funnel core and slag-metal interface, while far-off regions are discretized coarsely. Multiphase modeling on such partially refined meshes can be coupled with velocity formulations for inducing shear at slag-metal interface, derived on the basis of analytical and numerical modeling of gas-liquid plume during gas injection. Moreover, exploring shear interactions of steel and slag in the peripheral region of such plumes can serve for understanding the microscopic entrainment behavior at slag-metal interface and general underlying slag-metal interaction physics.

4. Conclusion

The observed prediction errors in the turbulent multiphase numerical model emphasize the scope of improvement in fundamental modeling and computation of steelmaking flow dynamics. The insights from investigation and subsequent discussion encourage a deeper look at fundamental physical and mathematical understanding of steelmaking hydrodynamics under influences of external sources of velocity, critical criteria for microscopic onset of slag entrainment. Moreover, the search for new robust and suitable numerical treatments is important to tackle flow physics with maximum relevance on the spectrum of generality and realism.

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